

ACADEMIC MOBILITY IN ENHANCING SCIENTIFIC POTENTIAL

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Abstract. Today, as a result of the reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan, significant attention is being paid to the education sector. This thesis examines the importance of academic mobility in enhancing scientific potential. It explains how the knowledge and experience of students and researchers increase through studying or conducting research in other countries. It also highlights how such opportunities contribute to the emergence of new ideas, the improvement of the quality of scientific work, and the development of international cooperation. The information presented in the thesis shows that academic mobility has a positive impact not only on the quality of education but also on the future professional activities of young people.

Keywords: Erasmus+, DAAD, Fulbright, international grant, international program, brain drain.

In the context of ongoing globalization, the issues of developing the education system at the international level and training competitive professionals have become increasingly important. In particular, academic mobility—defined as the study and research activities of students, teachers, and researchers at foreign higher education institutions—is recognized as one of the key directions of modern education. According to statistical data, more than 2.7 million students worldwide are currently studying abroad, which indicates the large-scale development of academic mobility¹.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention has also been paid in recent years to aligning the higher education system with international standards, enhancing scientific potential, and ensuring the integration of young people into the global knowledge space. In particular, as a result of the reforms implemented between 2017 and 2023, international cooperation in the higher education system has expanded, and opportunities for joint programs and academic exchange with foreign universities have significantly increased². The development of academic mobility has been identified as one of the priority directions of state policy. For instance, international programs such as Erasmus+, DAAD, and Fulbright are creating broad opportunities for students and academic staff. For example, within the Erasmus+ program alone, more than 3,000 Uzbek students and specialists have participated in international exchanges in recent years³.

In addition, academic mobility is identified as a particularly important direction in strategic documents aimed at developing the education system. Specifically, in reforms focused on the modernization of higher education and strengthening international integration, mobility is

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Academic_mobility

² <https://erasmus-networks.ec.europa.eu/book-page/country-page-uzbekistan>

³ https://uza.uz/en/posts/the-eus-role-in-uzbekistans-transformation-supporting-human-development-and-education_774906

regarded as “one of the key tools for improving the quality of education and developing scientific cooperation.” Therefore, academic mobility is considered an essential factor not only in improving the quality of education and scientific potential but also in strengthening a country’s competitiveness on the international stage. Currently, academic mobility and international scientific cooperation in Uzbekistan are developing rapidly. In recent years, special attention has been paid by the state to modernizing the higher education system and integrating it into the global arena. As a result, cooperation with foreign universities, joint programs, and academic exchanges have expanded significantly. In particular, in accordance with the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the concept for the development of the higher education system until 2030 defines the expansion of international cooperation and the enhancement of academic mobility as priority tasks⁴.

Today, higher education institutions in Uzbekistan are cooperating with leading universities around the world. For example, through the European Union’s Erasmus+ program, exchange programs have been established with many universities, enabling students and academic staff to gain international experience⁵. Similarly, through Germany’s DAAD organization, Uzbek students have opportunities to study at German universities⁶. The Fulbright program of the United States serves to support research activities and promote academic exchange⁷. In recent years, the number of branches of foreign higher education institutions in Uzbekistan has also increased significantly. Currently, more than 30 foreign universities operate in the country, including universities from the United Kingdom, Russia, South Korea, and other countries⁸. This provides students with the opportunity to receive education that meets international standards.

As a result of academic mobility, the achievements of students and young researchers have also been increasing significantly. In particular, the number of students receiving international grants and scholarships has been growing. Within the Erasmus+ program, thousands of Uzbek students have had the opportunity to study and undergo training at European universities⁹. Moreover, academic mobility has a positive impact on the effectiveness of scientific activity as well. According to research, scholars with international experience publish more scientific articles, and their work is cited more frequently¹⁰.

As a result of reforms in the higher education system, the coverage of education has also expanded. While in 2016 the higher education enrollment rate was around 9%, in recent years this figure has exceeded 30%¹¹. This indicates that educational opportunities for young people are expanding. In recent years, academic mobility indicators in Uzbekistan have increased significantly, clearly demonstrating the country’s integration into the global educational space. According to official data, in 2025, 28,954 Uzbek students went abroad for education, which represents a 19.3% decrease compared to 2024¹². At the same time, during January–August 2025, the departure of 20,700 students abroad was recorded¹³. Based on these data, it can be

⁴ <https://lex.uz/docs/4545884>

⁵ <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.daad.de/en/>

⁷ <https://foreign.fulbrightonline.org/>

⁸ <https://edu.uz/>

⁹ <https://erasmusplus.uz/>

¹⁰ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2203.06995>

¹¹ <https://stat.uz/>

¹² <https://kun.uz/en/02692026>

¹³ <https://kun.uz/en/news/2025/10/15/uzbekistan-sees-decline-in-outbound-students-rising-interest-in-east-asia>

observed that, on average, between 25,000 and 35,000 students go abroad each year for education. In addition, overall indicators remain high. In particular, as of 2023, more than 150,500 Uzbek students were studying at foreign higher education institutions, which has placed the country among the leading nations in terms of the number of students studying abroad¹⁴. The dynamics of statistical data also indicate positive growth trends.

Table 1¹⁵

Number of students studying abroad in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Years	Number of students
2015	28 100
2016	32 900
2017	35 000
2018	42 300
2019	53 000

In 2015, the number of students studying abroad was 28.1 thousand, while by 2019 this figure had reached 53 thousand¹⁶. In the following years, a sharp increase was observed, and by 2023 the number had exceeded 150 thousand. Additionally, according to international organizations, Uzbekistan’s outbound mobility rate is approximately 12%, meaning that 12 out of every 100 students pursue their education abroad¹⁷. These indicators confirm that academic mobility in Uzbekistan remains at a relatively high level. Summarizing the statistical data, on average, 25,000 to 30,000 Uzbek students go abroad for education each year, while the total number of students studying abroad exceeds 150 thousand. The above analysis shows that academic mobility in Uzbekistan has developed significantly in recent years and is actively supported by the state. As a result of the expansion of international programs, cooperation with foreign higher education institutions, and reforms in the education system, new opportunities are being created for students and young researchers. This, in turn, is accelerating the process of increasing the country’s scientific potential, acquiring modern knowledge and experience, and integrating into the global educational space. At the same time, despite the positive changes, certain challenges still remain in the academic mobility system. In particular, the unequal distribution of opportunities across regions, insufficient awareness among students about international programs, a low level of foreign language proficiency, and financial constraints hinder the further expansion of mobility.

To address these challenges and further develop academic mobility, a systematic approach is required. First of all, in order to ensure regional equity, it is important to strengthen international relations departments in all higher education institutions and introduce special quotas for students from remote areas. At the same time, it is necessary to increase students’ awareness by creating a unified online platform that aggregates information about grants and exchange programs, as well as organizing regular seminars and training sessions at universities. In addition, strengthening language preparation is one

¹⁴<https://yuz.uz/en/news/uzbekistan-zanimaet-trete-mesto-v-mire-po-kolichestvu-studentov-obuchayuxsya-zarubejom>

¹⁵ Prepared by the Statistics Agency. Author’s compilation

¹⁶ <https://stat.uz/en/press-center/news-of-committee/21989-xorijda-tahsil-olayotgan-talabalar-soni-3>

¹⁷<https://tradingeconomics.com/uzbekistan/outbound-mobility-ratio-all-regions-both-sexes-percent-wb-data.html>

of the most urgent tasks. Organizing preparatory courses for international exams such as IELTS and TOEFL in higher education institutions, as well as enhancing foreign language teaching from the early stages, will expand students' access to international programs. From a financial perspective, it is necessary to support talented youth by allocating additional state grants and scholarships, as well as establishing educational funds in cooperation with the private sector. From the standpoint of improving scientific potential, it is important to expand joint research projects between universities and to organize short-term scientific internships for professors and teaching staff.

At the same time, creating employment incentives for young people who have studied abroad and involving them in scientific projects can help reduce the “brain drain” problem. From a financial perspective, increasing the number of state grants and scholarships to support talented but financially disadvantaged students, as well as establishing educational funds with the participation of the private sector, can serve as an effective solution. In the modern context, the development of digital mobility is also important. By introducing online exchange programs and joint courses based on distance learning, it is possible to involve more students in the international education process. Overall, the systematic development of academic mobility plays a significant role in the educational, scientific, and innovative development of Uzbekistan. If the proposed measures are implemented consistently, the country's scientific potential will further increase, ensuring its *достой* place in the international educational space.

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